

Harvesting and Drying.

Harvesting is done when the grain develop the black layer at the point of attachment to the panicle.

Threshing.

Threshing is done after harvesting and drying by beating the earheads with a stick or by trampling bullocks. Then impurities should be removed by winnowing

Storage

Threshed grain is stored in gunny bags and put on palletes to allow free air circulation and avoid moisture buildup .

USES OF PEARL MILLET

Food

Pearl millet grain contains higher gross energy than corn, higher concentrations of amino acids, and 27–32% more protein (Gulia et al., 2007)

Feed/forage

it can be fed as grass for grazing, hay, silage or green chop. Grazing should be done when the crop reaches about 3feet or about 80cm tall.

Cover crop/green manure

Pearl millet grows rapidly producing 3-5 ton/ac of dry matter biomass which can be used as soil cover to minimise soil erosion while the high root density, root dry matter, and vegetative vigor helps to break up compacted soils It is compatible in mixes with forage legumes like cowpea and lab lab.

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CLUSTER GRANARY SEED PROJECT NaSARRI

Pearl Millet Production Guide

Funded by the:
European Union

Introduction

Pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*), also known as bulrush, cattail or candle millet, is the most drought and soil acid tolerant cereal. It withstands long spells of drought with the ability to regenerate productive nodal and basal tillers to compensate for losses caused by unfavourable conditions. This makes it the most assured cereal crop for drought-prone areas of Uganda. It is grown mainly in northern (Kitgum, Lamwo, Pader and Agago), northeastern (Kaabong and Kotido) and eastern Uganda where Teso region (especially Katakwi and Kumi districts) dominates. It has local names such as raa in Acholi, erau in Karamajong and mawele in Ateso. It is grown for food and to some extent income.

Adaptation

Pearl millet grows relatively well in a wide range of soils and climatic conditions but does best in well-drained sandy or light loam soils, and can survive low pH and low fertility. It grows well under a wide range of altitude but performs better below 2000m above sea level and temperature range of 25°C to 35°C and annual rainfall as low as 350mm.

Land preparation

Pearl millet requires a fine seed-bed which should be free from clods. Its seeds are very small in size. All crop residues, crop volunteers and weeds should be completely buried.

Planting

The seeds should be sown when there is moisture in the soil up to a depth of 2 to 3 cm. About 5 kg seed of pearl millet is sufficient for one hectare area.

A spacing of 45 cm between rows and 10-12 cm between plants is followed. The seed germinates and emerges fairly quickly, approximately 5 days after planting.

Intercropping

Pearl millet is normally mixed with other cereals such as finger millet, sorghum and maize. However, it is advisable to intercrop with legumes such as groundnuts, pigeon pea and cow pea in the ratio of 1 row of pearl millet to 2 rows of the legume.

Fertiliser application

Pearl millet has a deep root system which enables the crop to scavenge for residual nutrients which leads to fast growth and making it a good choice for low-input sustainable agricultural systems. However, micro-dosing with 6g NPK (15:15:15) followed by 2g DAP and finally 1g of UREA per plant results in a yield increase of 44%.

Weeding

Good weed control is necessary for a successful crop, and it is particularly important to control early emerging weeds. Hand weeding twice on 15 and 30 days after sowing thus (3-5 weeks).

Diseases

The common diseases of economic importance include; ergot (honey disease), covered kernel smut, rust and blast.

Pearl millet affected by diseases

However, pearl millet being a low value crop, use of cultural practices including early planting, use of resistant varieties, crop rotation, timely weeding etc. as an affordable pest control option for both pests and diseases. Pollination is better when the rainfall is less.

Insect pests and control

Common insect pests include stem borers particularly common in the Karamoja region, and sucking bugs in other growing areas.